

THE FORMS OF THE GAME IN SILENT FILMS, THE DISCOVERY OF SOUND TECHNOLOGY

Creative and Performing Arts
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Hazir Haziri

Faculty of Arts. University of Prishtina. Republic of Kosova.

Abstract

The soundless films of the first generation of world’S cinematography, which left an indelible mark and survived to this day, precisely because it was an undisputed artistic value. The universal themes selected and handled by Artists of that time will find a special focus on my work, the playfulness of the act of that time, the possibilities of recording in the celluloid and the appearance of obstacles with the mechanical projectors. The discovery of that period, that is recording the tone, the difficulties, the problems and the main challenges in acting in front of the film camera, such an invention would certainly give another direction to the artistic film, contribute to its development but at the same time exhibited barricades of banal nature, in the simple sense would turn the role-play to the zero point, precisely in the moments of its advancement towards the extreme naturalness, would bump into the theater actors with those of the sketches or the noisless films that had already had taken the good hand in front of the film camera, while the theater actors who had the strong gun, the speech in front of the vibrant audience were already starting their career and fighting with the film they would meditate on just as they were.

Introduction

It is widely known that the film has its origin due to the recording of "scenes" or various events in celluloid, which was an invention of particular importance, for the fact that it recorded the movements of people, objects and everything that the cameraman intended with his cinematographic camera. The most creative invention and technological possibilities of that time, obviously was the appearance of these films, through the mechanical projector, in various improvised halls.

Over time, the film took its course, thus investing individuals, and later groups of artists who organized various movie clips, which were "lighter" and much liked by the public at that time, while cinematic business got under way and had its development over the years, trying to bring technological innovations that help or challenge the entire production, including the game, or movie acting.

The film as a confession of audio-visual event that contains time, space, affinity, and conflict in itself, if we considered it to be a science, we would rightly state that it is a construction over all sciences, without ignoring the artistic side which undoubtedly holds the place over all the arts.

The First Films and the Game on them

Acting in silent films is largely based on body language and its expression through movements, which have often been similar to the classic theater, pantomime, circus movements, and only later to the logical control of the actions.

The treatment of acting methods was mainly of a melodramatic style which was carried out as a result of the earlier activity of the creators of that time, such as their actress background as dancer, scenic actor, concert actor, circus actor, etc.

The first films that were recorded had many challenges, including the technological hindrance of that time. The silent images were produced and broadcasted as such, due to the fact that technology support was lacking.

In those films, dialogue is usually transmitted through body language, through the dynamic game, the conflict that occurs between the characters and their relationship, not to overlook the relationship with the objects, the requisites and the parts of the scenography.

Soundless film implies fluency, play, situation, conflict, relationship, and everything else that is reflected within the film, and all of these are not synchronized as a voice-figure ratio and other tonic accompanying effects.

In the noiseless films we often see, where there is a lack of broadcasting, or the arrival of a movie author's message to the public, exactly there we can see a text describing the situation in which the characters are found or acting.

Soundless films are usually accompanied by music, which in most cases is played live, where before the design of the film, the first instrumentalists have appeared and with them is shown the film, this is noticed by the artist when we see the silent films, especially in escorting the scenes, the rhythm of music dictates the rhythm of the scene and vice versa, the music genre dictates or follows the genre that is dealt within that scene or film.

When we see it nowadays the shape of the game and compare it with the latter, which obviously creates the distance between the natural and the exaggeration of the actor's actions, we realize that the people of that time have long liked the art, especially the game, which it has served as fun and as a form of awareness, we see the best in dealing with the topics that make the authors of that time, topics that mainly had to do with daily life, with the reality that reigned that world, with the drawbacks of the systems of that time, which only art alone can show up.

The artists we call, or the productions that have researched and then dealt with such topics, must have had the courage and the skill to find a good author, so that those themes turn into sketches that would bring laughter to the public and of course the basic message will be conveyed subconsciously, always aiming at the comic element that best and most easily hits and penetrates the viewer's mind.

The Game as Perfection

The soundless film, in the absence of recording, especially in designing of the tune, the actor of that time gave very challenging tasks in front of the camera, organizing such scenes with

the help of the screenwriter or director, even there was almost no screenwriter and director during that time, as the scenes mostly directed, written, directed by the actor himself, who was himself a director, producer and everything else in that project (like Chaplin, Buster Keaton, Griffith, and many others until the late stage of cinema development).

During the study of the creativity of soundless films and analysis of the actor's game in particular, by not overlooking the whole process of creating a film, with all stages of production, we rightly find that the kind of treatment of the game of actors of that time in the silent movies, has obviously been more difficult. So, an entire process of staging scenes, or scenic parts, instantaneous sketches, or prepared for filming, with the technical tonic barrier (which did not exist at that time the possibility of recording the tune in the celluloid), we rightly consider that the actor of that time faced the most fundamental difficulties, in today's case, even with the advancement of film technology to the perfection of the last word, I would say that every contemporary actor would hesitate, or rather say that he would be scared from such a challenge.

So the actor's role in the silent films, of course, had a strong weapon, the imagination of the actor, who through body movements and mimicry aimed to bring to the perfection the information of the event that appeared in that piece of film. Anyone who was gifted to use the body language that was more familiar to the theater with the live play, was the wanted and liked actor in the public of that time.

In the usual cases, for the goodwill or even for the study, critique, if we are given the chance to watch the soundless films, we will surely encounter and learn that film dialogue is also displayed through body language, physical expression, mimicry, through realizing real situations with social identification problems. Even the writers who carried the dialogue or scriptwriters were not even needed, as these works were performed by the attendees who were orchestrating themselves through movements.

The best cases to describe the actress of that time are found in the silent films of the great cinema artists, for example films of Ch. Chaplin, which was liked at that time and created the first film audience.

Charlie Chaplin, at a younger age, began his career and became a dancer, then at the age of 14 he began his activities on stage as an actor. Later he went at the show as a comedian, where he was given the chance to travel to America with Fred Karno Repertoire Company.¹

He was soon accepted by the American audience of that time, even with his character in the sketch "A Night in an English Music Hall". Somewhere in 1912 Chaplin was awarded with a contract by Motion Picture. Initially, he worked for Mack Sennet and Keystone Film Company and was paid 150 dollars a week.

¹ Karno, Fred, Repertori i kompanise https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Fred_Karno

Thus, Chaplin began with the slow recording of the scenes which were constructed as such, to be understood by the audience. Appreciating his creativity in soundless cinema, as in the first sketches he contracted as screenwriter, actor and director, as well as in later productions with silent films that were serious products of his own, we rightly point out that his genius to select very interesting topics, which by the nature of the treatment allowed Chaplin to stretch his character well and place comic scenes in quite tragic situations for his charismatic character, who in every scene, or film pieces, was treated with different forms of interpretation, preserving its creative originality and of course the line of character which he had created and as such enjoyed by the public of that time, and is likewise liked to the present day.

Another segment that wins one's heart while watching Chaplin's films is the selection of topics and the way how those topics are covered, in the first plan if we are asking people for the name Chaplin, everyone will say at least one word, speaking for his comic character, or films, his comic sketches, or someone would say that s(he) is still having fun with his films. On the other hand, seeing the economic and political difficulties of that time and paying close attention to see that Chaplin has dealt with very tragic topics that he has brought to the public by deriding those issues through his tragic character in particular situations with the most common problems, or even more complex nature such as corruption, unemployment, attacking so administrations, state, etc. When we discuss for such topics, of course Chaplin has also addressed emotional topics, such as unhappy love, always using it as a bait to deal with other specifics, with which the public in some form is extremely entertained.

So, Chaplin and the form of his interpretation was special and today is treated as such and it is rightly ascertained that he has orchestrated many original situations within his silent films, making the game very natural and reliable for the public, just about his character with body movement, even in chaplin's movies, one can easily say that dialogue between the spoken language can hardly be felt.

Chaplin was putting a lot of importance to the body language, presenting it his whole figure interestingly, so in almost all movies there is the same figure, but transformed into different situations, such as joy, sorrow, laughter and crying, depending on where it has happened, or the story of what has happened.

Another important fact about Chaplin which contributed greatly to the process and development of cinematography was the creation of the Unated Artist Cooperation, which served for the legitimacy and regulation of finances, i.e., the income of filmmakers and the way how and how much these films would appear, other two founders were Mary Pickford, Griffith, Doglas Fairbanks.²

Another form of handling the game in front of the film camera in the silent films is the mastery of great actor Buster Keaton, who would have been influenced by the time at which Chaplin worked.

² United Artist of Corporation https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/United_Artists#The_early_years

The creativity of the actor Keaton also belongs to the film without sound, he was also special about the way of the game with the whole body and in concrete situations, assisting also through the film language that was already in existence since the logical flow of linking the movie plans to the montage had began to be applied, the actor was already offered and followed in details with Griffith.³

The example of a film already complete with the tale inside it and the main protagonists we found in the film “Buster Keaton's General” which tells about the life of a boy who loves a girl at the time of war turbulences when young people were volunteering to go to the war, the boy played by Buster Keaton does not meet the criteria to be a warrior and as such is rejected by a girlfriend who was then robbed and the whole war was made by the main character Keaton in order to return his girlfriend.

The particular feature of this film is to be carried on the train, following the other train, so the possibility of filming such a scene is very difficult even today, in this respect the author Keaton exceeds his colleagues by creating new situation and adapting his game in direct relationship with the object, in this case the locomotive that drives and the requisites that lie in it, which helps and hinders the achievement of the goal, but on the other hand, are very helpful in the actor's case, where Keaton's acting becomes very spontaneous, very reliable and of course interesting to the public, which through those actions follows the event in which he has become the main protagonist.

Keaton also plays with close plans and here we have the use of the face, through which he carries concrete emotions. Language, or film dialogue in this part is through its body with concrete actions, facing many challenges during its realization. Even with this author artistically is not noticed the lack of the spoken dialogue.

Challenges Displayed in the First Tune-Ups of the Movie

With the discovery of the voice recorder in the film there has been a change in the hiring of actors in Hollywood. The request arose for directors who understood the power of speech and had experience in the theater, leading studios to recruit directors and actors from New York's Broadway. The actors of the scene experienced in the dialogue were also employed in large numbers during 1930s. Some of the greatest attractions of the new media came from the vaudeville and the music theater, bringing artists such as Al Jolson, Eddie Cantor, Jeanette MacDonald and Brothers Marx. Edward G. Robinson, Humphrey Bogart, Paul Muni, Melvyn Douglas, Leslie Howard and Katharine Hepburn were also among those who came to film from the scene. And the drama itself was bought by the studios to become movies. More than 25 percent of performances produced during the 1930s were purchased by film studios. Voicing also helped to change the film business structure that led to consolidation and growth of the best positioned companies.

³ Brown, Karl (Kevin Brownlow, ed.) *Adventures with D. W. Griffith* New York: Farrar, Sturges & Giroux, 1973.

With the discovery of technological ability for the voice recording of the film and its synchronous design together with the picture, the artists of that era of film are faced and challenged with new practices, completely different from the experience in front of the camera in the silent film. Here in the soundtrack film, besides the innovation of the time, which was welcomed and echoed by the public of that time, on the other hand, the filmmakers were turned back two decades ago, to the time where they had taken off the theater, right at the moment when the final division with the Theater had already begun, when the game in the film sounded far beyond the natural course. With the introduction of voice in celluloid, the word was added to the actor, which until then was "denied", along with the actors, there were created many opportunities for the other film sectors, starting from writers-scriptwriters who many wrote for the theater, now new stage adaptations focusing on dialogue, had to adapt to the film. From theaters were also taken actors who were more "free" in the interpretation of dialogues or monologues and as such, the first actress-looking films we almost play the theater, even though the language of the film was already used, the flow of plans, disaggregating the event, was already very logical, the spectator of that time even watched the film exactly with the filmed and disaggregated event. So imposedly the need for theater actors appeared, not knowing well the form of secession and the play of the game, in the most realistic way. By browsing the Oscars price history, we see the first awards for the best actor and actress in the first edition, 1929, where the best actor award belongs to actress Janet Gaynor in "7th Heaven", "Street Angel", "Sunrise " directed by Frank Borzage; while the best male actor was Emil Jannings in "The Last Command", "The Way of All Flesh" directed by Jose von Stenberg, all these awards are given in the silent film. Meanwhile, in 1930, we will have two prize-sharing, best-selling prizes, best-selling films, in that year Mary Pickford was awarded for the film "Coquette" directed by Teylor and best actor Warner Baxter in the film "In Old Arizona" directed by Irving Cummings while actress Marie Dressler in the film "Min and Bill" was directed by George W. Hill and was rewarded in 1931 and the best actor Lionel Barrymore "A Free Soul" directed by Clarence Brown. A difficult experience creating new competition struggles in acting followed the productive film industry for almost two decades. The aforementioned films also competed with the innovative changes they made, where for the moment they were rated with prestigious prices, but judging remotely, we can conclude that natural acting, in spite of the advancement of technology, takes somewhere from the 40s of the last century, when a great caste of actors created the right experience in front of the cameras in different movies and when the new cast of educated actors with a tendency to play in the movie came, then we can say that we have the advancement and the launch towards a new contemporary actuarial journey, which is now known in the history of the world cinematography is known as Acting of the Golden Age.

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